

The Institutional Determinants of Transitioning to a Higher Income Status: A Logistic Model Approach

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Abstract

This paper aims to empirically investigate the effect of institutional quality (IQ) on countries transitioning to higher income status. For this purpose, a logistic regression model was used in the study for countries classified as lower-middle income (LMIC) and upper-middle income (UMIC) between 2002 and 2019. Given the availability of the variables used in the study, the time series covers the years 2002-2019. Due to the limited time series, the analysis in this study was limited to 29 lower-middle income countries and 20 upper-middle income countries. In total, 49 countries were considered in this study. The results indicate that IQ is not mostly an effective factor in the transition from low-income to lower-middle-income. Conversely, IQ has mostly a positive effect on transition from LMIC to UMIC. In addition, government expenditures, one of the control variables, have a positive effect in all sub-models in both cases.

Keywords:

Economic Institutions,

Economic

Development,

Logit Regression,

Daha Yüksek Gelir Düzeyine Geçişin Kurumsal Belirleyicileri: Lojistik Model Yaklaşımı

Özet

Bu çalışma, kurumsal kalitenin ülkelerin daha yüksek gelir düzeyine geçişi üzerindeki etkisini ampirik olarak araştırmayı amaçlamaktadır. Bu amaç doğrultusunda çalışmada, 2002-2019 yılları arasında alt orta gelirli ve üst orta gelirli olarak sınıflandırılan ülkeler için lojistik regresyon modeli kullanılmıştır. Çalışmada kullanılan değişkenlerin mevcudiyeti göz önüne alındığında, zaman serisi 2002-2019 yıllarını kapsamaktadır. Zaman serisinin sınırlı olması nedeniyle, bu çalışmadaki analiz 29 alt orta gelirli ülke ve 20 üst orta gelirli ülkeyle sınırlandırılmıştır. Toplamda, bu çalışmada 49 ülke ele alınmıştır. Sonuçlar, kurumsal kalitenin düşük gelirli ülkelere alt orta gelirli ülkelere geçişte çoğunlukla etkili bir faktör olmadığını göstermektedir. Aksine, kurumsal kalitenin alt orta gelirli ülkelere üst orta gelirli ülkelere geçişte çoğunlukla olumlu bir etkisi bulunmaktadır. Ayrıca, kontrol değişkenlerinden biri olan kamu harcamaları, her iki durumda da tüm alt modellerde pozitif bir etkiye sahiptir.

Anahtar Kelimeler:

Ekonomik Kurumlar,

Ekonomik Kalkınma,

Lojistik Regresyon,

1. INTRODUCTION

The role of institutions has gained increasing attention, particularly following the contributions of North and Thomas (1973) and Acemoglu et al. (2004). North and Thomas (1973) emphasize that institutional arrangements, including property rights, incentivize growth-enhancing activities. Similarly, Acemoglu et al. (2004) argue that institutions shape investment in physical and human capital as well as technological progress, serving as endogenous determinants of growth.

Empirical literature on the effect of institutions on economic growth is relatively recent. Several empirical studies show that there is a positive effect of institutions on economic growth (Acquah et al., 2023; Law et al., 2013). Some studies indicate that different institutions have different effects on growth. Nevertheless, these studies reveal the effect of economic institutions on economic growth is positive and strong (Alexiou et al., 2020; de Almeida et al., 2024; Hussien, 2023; Nawaz, 2015).

The available studies provide evidence on whether and how institutions affect economic growth. However, they say nothing about the effect of institutions on the transitioning income status of countries. For instance, what is the effect of institutions on the transition from low - to lower-middle-income status? This paper addresses this gap by providing empirical evidence on the role of institutions in driving transitions across income levels. We present empirical evidence on the effect of institutions on the rise of countries' a higher income status (*lower-middle-income and, upper-middle-income following the classification of the World Bank*) using a logit regression model.

Given the availability of the variables used in this study, the time series extended from 2002 to 2019. Owing to the restricted nature of the time series, the analysis encompasses 29 countries with lower-middle-income status and 20 countries with upper-middle-income status. The structure of the paper is as follows. Section 2 provides a description of the dataset and model. Section 3 presents the empirical results, and Section 4 concludes the study.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Institutions are the rules of the game in a society. In other words, institutions shape interactions among individuals. Ultimately, institutions structure the political, social, and economic incentives of these interactions. Institutional change is the most fundamental factor determining how the social structure will evolve over time. It is well established that institutions affect the functioning of the economy. The nature and intensity of institutional change profoundly influence the performance exhibited by economies over time (North, 1999: 9).

According to the institutional thesis, societies that possess a social organization conducive to encouraging investment achieve higher levels of prosperity. In this context, thinkers such as J. Locke, A. Smith and F. Hayek have emphasized the importance of private property rights. Similarly, in more recent historical periods, numerous historians and economists have argued for the necessity of securing property rights (Acemoglu et al., 2002: 1262). For instance, North (1999) vigorously defends the view that institutions affect economic performance and links the sound organization of society to the safeguarding of property rights. From this perspective, there is a need for the existence and effective functioning of a set of political, economic, and social institutions that serve the interests of a broad segment of society (Acemoglu et al., 2002: 1262).

Institutions, by influencing behaviors and incentives in real life, possess the power to determine the success or failure of nations. While individual abilities are socially valuable, their transformation into positive outcomes is critically shaped by an institutional framework. Educational institutions facilitate the acquisition of free skills, whereas economic institutions enable facile investment initiatives. Trust in institutions and the rule of law they establish is of paramount importance. Political institutions, in turn, are regarded as guarantors of stability and continuity. These institutions determine the role of economic institutions in shaping countries' prosperity (Acemoglu and Robinson, 2018: 47).

According to Chong and Calderón (2000), frequent changes in the rules governing social relations, non-enforcement of contracts, the granting of broad discretionary powers to governments, inadequate protection of property rights, high levels of corruption and rent-seeking, and insufficient protection of low-income groups indicate problems in IQ. Examining the relationship between IQ and income distribution, Chong and Calderón (2000) find that IQ is positively associated with income inequality in poor countries, while it exhibits a negative relationship in developed countries. These results suggest that institutional reforms initially increase inequality but subsequently reduce it as improvements take hold. In less developed countries, the groups most affected in the early stages of institutional reforms are those in the informal economy. Consequently, institutional reforms

initially exacerbate inequalities, which then diminish as the informal economy adapts to the new regulations (Chong and Calderón, 2000: 781).

Highlighting the importance of institutional organization, Fukuyama (2014: 60-63) argues that successful state-building and institutional reforms require the presence of strong societal demand. In his view, the greatest obstacle to institutional development in underdeveloped countries is the insufficient demand for institutions and institutional reforms.

Since the beginning of the 21st century, advocates of development policy have largely converged on the view that “*institutions matter*”. This perspective is often presented under headings such as “*governance*”, “*state capacity*”, or “*institutional quality*”. Fukuyama (2014) identifies four fundamental dimensions of statehood in the context of institutional quality: organizational planning and management, design of the political system, foundations of legitimacy, and cultural and structural elements. Beyond this, many researchers regard political stability, government effectiveness, public expenditure on education, anti-corruption efforts, protection of property rights, and improvements in governance as determining factors in development and economic growth (Liko, 2024). In summary, institutionalization, democratization, and the effective implementation of governance are seen to exert a significant and positive impact on sustaining economic growth and development. This observation is supported by empirical studies.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

A review of the literature reveals numerous studies examining the relationships between organizational quality and growth, organizational quality and development, and institutionalization and income level. The study by Valeriani and Peluso (2011) examined whether there is a positive relationship between IQ and economic growth. The institutional indicators used in the study are civil liberties, the number of actors with veto power, and the quality of government. According to the results of the study, it is seen that the main claim of the study, that IQ positively affects economic growth, is supported.

The study by Nawaz et al. (2014) has two main objectives. Firstly, it theoretically examines the impact of institutions on economic growth. The theoretical model predicts that improved IQ will reduce rent-seeking activities, thus increasing income, and vice versa. However, the empirical results of the study reveal that institutions are indeed important in determining long-run economic growth in Asian economies.

In their study, Butkiewicz and Yanikkaya (2006) argue that country-specific characteristics have a significant effect on growth performance when analyzing the factors determining economic growth rates. Previous studies have shown that while the rule of law promotes economic growth, democratic institutions do not improve economic growth performance. However, these results are highly sensitive to sample selection and analysis techniques. When using the same country sample, it is observed that countries with democratic institutions exhibit higher growth performance. The analysis technique used in the relationship between growth and democratic institutions also plays a decisive role in the results obtained. In this context, estimations made using instrumental variable techniques show that democratic institutions have a positive effect on growth performance. These results are particularly important for developing countries.

The study by Asghar et al. (2015) examined the impact of IQ on economic growth in developing economies of Asia. Accordingly, the study used panel data from 13 developing countries in Asia for the period 1990-2013. The IQ index was constructed using the principal components analysis method. According to the results of the research, IQ has a positive effect on economic growth. The study emphasizes the need to improve IQ to enhance economic growth in the selected developing Asian countries.

Wandeda et al. (2021) examined the effect of IQ on economic growth in Sub-Saharan African countries for the period 2006-2018. Their findings showed that improvements in IQ positively and significantly boosted economic growth. Furthermore, the effect of IQ on growth varied depending on the regional location of the countries. Specifically, countries in the West African region showed that IQ was more effective in promoting income growth compared to East and Central Africa. In addition, the effect of IQ on economic growth also varied according to the income level of the countries; it was determined that improvements in IQ positively impacted the performance of low-income Sub-Saharan African economies more than middle-income countries. The study emphasizes the need to strengthen independent institutional structures that prosecute economic crimes, support policies aligned with the global development agenda, and strengthen institutions that expand the democratic space, civil liberties, and citizen participation in the country's development agenda.

Jahan et al. (2020) examined the relationship between IQ and “*formal*” income in their study. Their findings indicate that improvements in IQ tend to reduce informality and lead to an increase in formal income. However, this trend occurs at the expense of the informal economy and potentially negates perceived productivity gains. This study uses data from 5,506 Brazilian municipalities to examine the effects of IQ on total per capita income. It also reveals the effect of institutions on the size of the informal economy. The strongest finding of the study is that IQ is significantly related to development. Improvements in IQ reduce the informal economy and increase productivity.

According to an empirical study by Zhuang et al. (2010), developing Asian economies that scored higher on government effectiveness, regulatory quality, and rule of law grew faster on average than economies that scored below the global average during the 1998-2008. Based on these findings, it is argued that improving governance has a positive effect on development.

Blancheton and Chhorn (2021) examine the relationship between public expenditure and IQ and income inequality in Asia and the Pacific region. The study analyzes data from 1988-2014 using panel cointegration. The results show that government expenditure and IQ have negative long-run, balanced effects on income inequality in the Asia and Pacific region. The effect of IQ has only a unidirectional Granger causality link with income inequality. A nonlinear relationship was also found between government expenditure and institutional factors linked to income inequality. According to this, government expenditure reduces income inequality in countries with higher institutional development. Conversely, if institutional development is less, it increases income inequality.

The study by Hunjra et al. (2023) analyzes the impact of IQ on sustainable development in 65 developing countries across various regions during the period 1984-2019. The results show that IQ has a positive effect on economic sustainability. Ivanya and Salerno (2021) conducted a study demonstrating the relationship between governance and economic growth. Mahran (2023), in her study covering 116 countries, attempted to analyze the impact of governance on economic growth. Yahyaoui and Bouchoucha (2021), in their study covering African countries, addressed the long-term relationship between governance and economic growth.

4. DATA, MODEL AND METHOD

The study uses annual data from 2002 to 2019, collected from the World Bank, United Nations, and International Monetary Fund databases. I construct the model using the variables control of corruption (*corr*), rule of law (*law*), regulatory quality (*regq*), government effectiveness (*goveff*), voice and accountability (*voa*) and political stability and absence of violence (*pols*). Additionally, the study check the robustness of the findings incorporating the variables of the sum of exports and imports/GDP (*open*), foreign direct investment/GDP (*fdi*), employment/population (*labour*), general government expenditure/GDP (*govexp*) and monetary sector credit to private sector/GDP (*credit*). The formulation of the model is as follows;

$$gdpps_{it} = \beta_1 corr_{it} + \beta_2 law_{it} + \beta_3 regq_{it} + \beta_4 govef_{it} + \beta_5 voa_{it} + \beta_6 pols_{it} + \beta_q controls_{it} + u_{it} \quad (1)$$

The dependent variables in the model are defined for each country group as follows;

- Gdpps for lower-middle income country: $gdpp \leq 1.145\$ = 0$; $gdpp > 1.145\$ = 1$
- Gdpps for upper-middle income country: $gdpp = (1.146\$, 4.515\$) = 0$; $gdpp = (4.516\$, 14.005\$) = 1$

In this study, “*lower-middle-income countries*” refer to countries that transitioned from the low-income group to the lower-middle-income group during the study period. Similarly, “*upper-middle-income countries*” refer to countries that transitioned from the lower-middle-income group to the upper-middle-income group during the study period.

To estimate the parameters of the models, we use the mixed-effects logistic regression model (Pineiro and Chao, 2006) with between-within approach (Neuhaus and Kalbfleisch, 1998; Neuhaus and McCulloch, 2006). The mixed-effects linear model assumes that

$$logit pr(Y_{ij} = 1 | \alpha_i, X_{ij}) = \alpha_i + \beta X_{ij} \quad (2)$$

with $\alpha \sim G$.

Then, X_{ij} into between ($\underline{X}_i = n_i^{-1} \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} X_{ij}$) and within-cluster ($X_{ij} - \underline{X}_i$) components and extend replaced βX_{ij} in Model 2 by $\beta_B \underline{X}_i + \beta_W (X_{ij} - \underline{X}_i)$ and the following form is obtained:

$$E(Y_{ij} | \alpha_i, X_{ij}) = \alpha_i + \beta_B \underline{X}_i + \beta_W (X_{ij} - \underline{X}_i) \quad (4)$$

Following the methodological framework described above, the subsequent section reports the empirical results of the analysis.

5. EMPIRICAL RESULTS

Table 1 reports descriptive statistics for LMIC. According to the table, the countries have a negative mean values in all institutional indicators. On the other hand, government expenditure, on average, is approximately 24% of GDP. Also, trade openness is relatively high. Its mean is approximately 81% of GDP.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics for LMIC

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
pergdpp	522	0.648	0.478	0.000	1.000
law	522	-0.616	0.435	-1.737	0.626
corr	522	-0.640	0.497	-1.597	1.590
regq	522	-0.572	0.357	-1.549	0.127
goveff	522	-0.604	0.480	-2.172	0.691
voa	522	-0.417	0.569	-1.538	0.596
pols	522	-0.501	0.756	-2.810	1.284
govexp	522	24.193	10.076	6.641	66.442
open	522	81.196	46.799	24.600	376.230
credit	522	27.889	18.472	2.010	108.032
labour	522	38.250	7.801	22.596	57.528
fdi	522	3.613	5.566	-37.170	43.910

Source: Authors' Calculations Based on the Data

Table 2 reports descriptive statistics for UMIC. According to Table 2, the countries have a negative mean values in all institutional indicators. On the other hand, government expenditure, on average, is approximately 28% of GDP. Also, trade openness is relatively high. Its mean is approximately 73% of GDP. In addition, the financial system is more developed than that in LMIC. The mean of credit is approximately 42% of GDP.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics for UMIC

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
pergdpp	360	0.558	0.497	0.000	1.000
law	360	-0.473	0.387	-1.205	0.457
corr	360	-0.450	0.417	-1.437	0.828
regq	360	-0.166	0.447	-1.388	1.032
goveff	360	-0.300	0.397	-1.175	0.775
voa	360	-0.237	0.607	-1.749	0.599
pols	360	-0.398	0.597	-2.376	1.201
govexp	360	28.535	9.386	12.477	49.417
open	360	72.735	29.354	9.723	146.820
credit	360	41.695	29.239	5.585	165.390
labour	360	39.599	9.773	15.946	57.351
fdi	360	4.450	4.895	-14.370	45.150

Table 3 presents variance inflation factor (VIF) results. According to the results, the VIF values are well below the commonly accepted threshold of 10 in the literature. Accordingly, there is no evidence of serious multicollinearity in the models.

Variable	LMIC		UMIC	
	VIF	1/VIF	VIF	1/VIF
law	5.65	0.177008	5.96	0.167797
goveff	3.27	0.30607	3.71	0.269379
corr	2.92	0.343032	4.49	0.222542
regq	2.78	0.360131	2.13	0.468503
credit	2.39	0.419176	1.75	0.570498
labour	2.36	0.422953	1.84	0.544264
voa	2.28	0.438762	1.86	0.537292
open	1.87	0.534753	1.95	0.512433
govexp	1.85	0.539223	1.52	0.659906
pols	1.34	0.748204	1.8	0.554363
fdi	1.17	0.851718	1.22	0.817608
Mean VIF	2.53		2.57	

Source: Authors' Calculations Based on the Data

Table 4 presents the correlation matrix for LMIC illustrating the pairwise relationships among the variables included in the analysis. The results indicate a positive correlation among institutional indicators in both country groups. Moreover, the strongest correlations are observed between these institutional variables. For instance, the correlation coefficient between *Law* and *Goveff* is approximately 0.7.

	pergdpp	law	corr	regq	goveff	Pols	voa	govexp	open	fdi	credit	labour
pergdpp	1.000											
law	0.047	1.000										
corr	0.053	0.820	1.000									
regq	0.026	0.603	0.375	1.000								
goveff	0.056	0.773	0.656	0.646	1.000							
pols	0.123	0.413	0.495	0.118	0.214	1.000						
voa	-0.002	0.526	0.345	0.466	0.412	0.114	1.000					
govexp	0.196	0.243	0.322	0.094	0.203	0.317	0.126	1.000				
open	0.105	0.036	0.161	0.026	0.053	0.380	-0.293	0.471	1.000			
fdi	0.082	-0.046	-0.073	-0.010	-0.063	0.222	-0.080	0.162	0.352	1.000		
credit	0.157	0.259	0.118	0.247	0.395	0.079	0.053	0.139	0.094	0.032	1.000	
labour	0.063	-0.112	-0.221	0.067	0.133	0.038	-0.121	-0.030	0.070	0.064	0.539	1.000

Source: Authors' Calculations Based on the Data

Table 5 presents the correlation matrix for UMIC providing insights into the strength and direction of associations among the variables used in the study.

Table 5. Correlation Matrix for UMIC

	pergdpp	law	corr	regq	goveff	Pols	voa	govexp	open	fdi	credit	labour
pergdpp	1											
law	0.282	1										
corr	0.053	0.727	1									
regq	0.165	0.674	0.488	1								
goveff	0.235	0.748	0.622	0.572	1							
pols	0.213	0.428	0.287	0.224	0.207	1						
voa	0.067	0.442	0.422	0.428	0.133	0.324	1					
govexp	0.310	0.335	0.314	-0.020	0.184	0.160	0.206	1				
open	-0.106	0.331	0.317	0.055	0.243	0.245	0.129	-0.110	1			
fdi	-0.121	0.081	0.146	0.084	0.036	0.116	0.049	-0.012	0.254	1		
credit	0.182	0.383	0.296	0.202	0.507	0.098	-0.305	0.019	0.181	-0.104	1	
labour	0.190	-0.081	-0.270	0.125	0.171	-0.102	-0.368	-0.361	-0.283	-0.092	0.408	1

Source: Authors' calculations based on the data.

Table 6 presents the results for lower-middle income countries. According to Table 6 institutional factors have not usually a statistically significant effect on the transition from low-income-status to lower-middle income status. However, only the political stability (pols) has a statistically significant effect. Moreover, since the coefficient of political stability is greater than one, the effect is positive. Among control variables the government expenditure (govexp) and the credit providing to private sector (credit) have a statistically significant and positive on the change of income status. Furthermore this effect is robust in terms of different models. Conversely, since the coefficient of labour is less than one, it has a statistically significant and negative effect in most models (except column 1.5).

Table 6. Results of LMIC

Independent Variables	Dependent Variable: gdpps												
	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.8	1.9	1.10	1.11	1.12	
law	0.81 (0.40)	0.96 (0.52)	0.99 (0.52)	0.71 (0.37)	0.91 (0.47)	0.82 (0.41)	0.86 (0.20)						
corr	0.63 (0.22)	0.76 (0.30)	0.72 (0.27)	1.13 (0.44)	1.03 (0.39)	0.75 (0.28)		0.92 (0.18)					
regq	0.45** (0.14)	1.10 (0.39)	0.70 (0.24)	0.97 (0.34)	0.93 (0.34)	0.49** (0.16)			0.95 (0.23)				
goveff	1.63 (0.49)	1.34 (0.46)	1.42 (0.45)	0.98 (0.33)	1.20 (0.39)	1.59 (0.48)				0.92 (0.18)			
voa	0.98 (0.19)	0.88 (0.18)	1.13 (0.23)	0.96 (0.21)	0.94 (0.19)	0.99 (0.19)					0.87 (0.16)		
pols	1.44** (0.20)	1.34** (0.20)	1.24 (0.18)	1.45** (0.23)	1.38** (0.21)	1.27 (0.20)							1.24 (0.16)
govexp		1.03*** (0.01)					1.03*** (0.01)	1.03*** (0.01)	1.03*** (0.01)	1.03*** (0.01)	1.04*** (0.01)	1.03*** (0.01)	
open			1.01*** (0.01)				0.99 (0.01)						
credit				1.02*** (0.01)			1.02*** (0.01)						
labour					1.02*** (0.01)		0.98** (0.01)	0.98** (0.01)	0.98** (0.01)	0.98** (0.01)	0.98** (0.01)	0.98** (0.01)	0.99 (0.01)
fdi						1.05** (0.02)	1.02 (0.02)						
Observation	522	522	522	522	522	522	522	522	522	522	522	522	522
Wald-prob.	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

Notes: Robust Standard Errors are in parenthesis. ***: p<0.01, **: p<0.05, *: p<0.1.

Source: Authors' calculations based on the data.

The results presented in Table 7 institutional factors have usually a statistically significant effect on the transition to upper-middle from lower-middle-income status. Among these, the rule of law (law) and political stability (pols) and the effectiveness of government (goveff) have a statistically positive effect in most models. Conversely, the effect of control of corruption (corr) is negative on the transition to upper-middle from lower-middle income status. Moreover, the government expenditure has a statistically significant and positive in all models and the effect of credit is so in most models. Conversely, the trade openness has a statistically significant and positive on the transition to upper-middle from lower-middle income status.

Table 7. Results of UMIC

Independent Variables	Dependent Variable: gdpps												
	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.8	1.9	1.10	1.11	1.12	
law	2.65* (1.50)	11.73** (7.14)	4.11** (2.39)	6.33** (3.71)	18.23** (13.17)	2.77* (1.60)	8.58** (3.28)						
corr	0.10** (0.05)	0.14*** (0.07)	0.12** (0.06)	0.13** (0.06)	0.20*** (0.10)	0.10** (0.05)		1.54 (0.50)					
regq	1.19 (0.44)	0.93 (0.33)	1.09 (0.40)	0.80 (0.30)	0.55 (0.22)	1.17 (0.44)			2.44** (0.66)				
goveff	3.69** (1.93)	2.25 (1.12)	2.96** (1.49)	2.05 (1.00)	1.59 (0.80)	3.66** (1.91)				4.08** (1.38)			
voa	1.20 (0.29)	0.91 (0.22)	1.11 (0.27)	1.46 (0.37)	1.16 (0.28)	1.20 (0.29)					1.78** (0.38)		
pols	1.44* (0.31)	1.69** (0.39)	1.45* (0.32)	1.48* (0.34)	1.54* (0.35)	1.43* (0.31)						2.73** (0.55)	
govexp		1.04*** (0.01)					1.05** (0.01)	1.04** (0.01)	1.05** (0.01)	1.05** (0.01)	1.04** (0.01)	1.05** (0.01)	
open			1.01* (0.01)				0.98** (0.01)	0.98** (0.01)	0.99** (0.01)	0.99** (0.01)	0.98** (0.01)	0.98** (0.01)	
credit				1.01** (0.01)			0.99 (0.01)	1.01* (0.01)	1.01** (0.01)	1.01 (0.01)	1.02** (0.01)	1.01* (0.01)	
labour					1.03*** (0.01)		1.04** (0.01)	1.01 (0.01)	0.99 (0.01)	1.01 (0.01)	1.01 (0.01)	1.01 (0.01)	
fdi							1.01 (0.02)	0.94 (0.04)	0.95 (0.03)	0.94 (0.04)	0.94 (0.04)	0.96 (0.04)	0.94 (0.04)
Observation	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360
Wald-prob.	0.000	0.0000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

Notes: Robust Standard Errors are in parenthesis. ***: p<00.1, **: p<0.5, *: p<0.1

Source: Authors' calculations based on the data.

The implications of the findings obtained from this analysis are elaborated on and critically discussed in the following section.

6. CONCLUSION

This paper provides empirical evidence the economic and institutional factors that influence countries' transition from low-income status to LMIC status and from lower-middle-income status to UMIC status. The results for LMIC show that institutional factors, other than political stability, do not affect the transition from low-income to lower-middle income status. On the other hand, the effect of labor is negative. This result may be related to the law of diminishing returns, as these countries have less physical capital. The most effective factors in

transitioning to higher income status in these countries are government expenditures and credits given to the private sector.

The results for upper-middle income countries show that institutional factors, other than control of corruption, positively affect the transition from lower-income to upper-middle income status. An increase in control of corruption negatively affects the transition to UMIC status. This result regarding corruption is consistent with the view known in the literature as the 'grease the wheels' hypothesis. Some studies show that corruption can have positive effects on economic growth in the face of an ill functioning bureaucracy and inefficient government policies (Cooray and Schneider, 2018; De Soto, 1989; Dreher and Gassenbner, 2013; Leff, 1964). On the other hand, the trade openness has a negative effect on transition to upper-middle income status. Conversely, the government expenditure has a strong effect on the transition to UMIC status.

Finally, the results obtained from 49 countries with different income levels highlight that the effect of IQ on economic development varies across income levels. However, government expenditure is a factor that positively affects economic development across all income levels. The results also show that these countries have not benefited from globalization in terms of economic development.

While factors such as government expenditures and credit seem to be sufficient for the rise in income status at lower income levels, the contribution of IQ also seems to be necessary at higher income levels. Therefore, increasing IQ may be an effective way to escape the middle-income trap. Also, the result regarding corruption imply that these countries need to pass in review their bureaucratic structures and government policies.

The study period is limited by data availability and the inability to include a larger set of countries. Accordingly, the findings should be interpreted with caution and cannot be broadly generalized. Future research may contribute more generalizable evidence by addressing these limitations through extended datasets and wider country coverage.

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